

EPR spectral and redox properties of some 2,9-dimethyl-1,10-phenanthroline copper(II) complexes

Krishna Srivastava, Divya Srivastava, Mala Kumari, Subhasni Khare and Jagdish Prasad*

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002, India

E-mail : dr_jagdish_p@yahoo.co.in; dr_krishna_s@yahoo.co.in

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The redox behaviour of $[\text{Cu}(\text{dmp})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (1), $[\text{Cu}(\text{dmp})_2]\text{SO}_4$ (2), $[\text{Cu}(\text{dmp})_2\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (3) and $[\text{Cu}(\text{dmp})_2\text{Br}]\text{Br}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (4) has been investigated in 50% aqueous-ethanol/0.2 M NaClO_4 and absolute ethanol/TBAP at GCE by means of cyclic voltammetry. All these complexes show a quasi-reversible couple $\text{Cu}^{2+/+}$ with formal potential, $E^0 = +430$ to $+650$ mV vs SCE in the potential range $+1.0$ to -0.2 V vs SCE. Analysis of CV data shows that the electrode process for complex 3 involves ECE mechanism in absolute ethanol/0.1 M TBAP medium. An unusual and complicated electrochemical behaviour has been observed for this complex in 50% aqueous-ethanol/0.2 M NaClO_4 medium due to the presence of more than one complex species in solution. The reduction potentials, E_{pc1} ($\text{Cu}^{2+/+}$) for complexes 2 and 4 in 50% aqueous-ethanol medium are almost similar at a given scan rate. However, the ease of reduction decreases (i.e. E_{pc1} becomes less positive) in the order : $1 > 4 > 3$ in absolute alcohol/0.1 M TBAP medium. Powdered and frozen solution EPR spectra (77 K) of these complexes have also been studied and the results are interpreted.

The redox properties of copper complexes explain their role as catalysts of a large variety of processes. Thus in biological systems copper enzymes are involved in dioxygen transport, in monooxygenases, in dioxygenases, in oxidases, and in electron transfer processes¹⁻³. Also a large variety of organic reactions⁴ are catalyzed by $\text{Cu}^0/\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$ and/or Cu^{I} salts. Many of these reactions are initiated by a redox process, i.e. the Cu^{I} redox properties are crucial to these processes. $\text{Cu}^{\text{II/I}}$ electron transfer redox reactions are also currently of interest because the structural difference between the two oxidation states place unusual constraints on the electron-transfer kinetics⁵. Insight into this behaviour has application in understanding and manipulating the properties of cuproproteins. Examples of small molecules coordination number invariant are rare. This paper describes a detailed EPR spectral and redox behaviours of some four- and five-coordinate copper(II) complexes of 2,9-dimethyl-1,10-phenanthroline (dmp).

Results and discussion

The redox behaviours of 2 mM solution of $[\text{Cu}(\text{dmp})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (1), $[\text{Cu}(\text{dmp})_2]\text{SO}_4$ (2), $[\text{Cu}(\text{dmp})_2\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (3) and $[\text{Cu}(\text{dmp})_2\text{Br}]\text{Br}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (4) were investigated both in absolute alcohol containing 0.1 M tetrabutyl ammonium perchlorate (TBAP) and in 50% aqueous-alcoholic solution (v/v) containing 0.2 M NaClO_4 at GCE

by means of cyclic voltammetry with scan rate ranging from 10 to 300 mV s^{-1} . CV parameters for these complexes are given in Tables 1 (0.1 M TBAP/absolute alcohol), 2 and 3 (in 0.2 M NaClO_4 /50% aqueous-alcoholic medium). Figs. 1(A) and 1(B) illustrate the typical cyclic voltammograms of complex 3 in 0.1 M TBAP/absolute alcohol and 0.2 M NaClO_4 /50% aqueous-alcoholic media, respectively at 50 mV s^{-1} .

One redox couple, $\text{Cu}^{2+/+}$ (c_1/a_1) appears in the potential range from $+1.0$ to -0.2 V vs SCE in the case of complexes 1, 2 and 4. Controlled-potential coulometry shows the involvement of a single electron per molecule for this reduction step. Analysis of the cyclic voltammetric data for the $\text{Cu}^{2+/+}$ couple showed the following features : the anodic to cathodic peak current ratio ($I_{\text{pa1}}/I_{\text{pc1}}$) is 1.0, indicating a simple electron-transfer reaction⁶. Also the value of ΔE_p ($E_{\text{pa1}} - E_{\text{pc1}}$) progressively increases from 60 to 120 mV and the cathodic peak potential (E_{pc1}) shifts cathodically (more negative) with increasing scan rate. Both these observations are indicative of the heterogeneous quasi-reversible one-electron transfer process. The plot of I_{pc1} or I_{pa1} vs $v^{1/2}$ gives a straight line passing through origin, showing that the electrode process is diffusion-controlled⁶. It should be mentioned that the Cu^{II} ion is coordinated with four N atoms of the two dmp molecules in a distorted tetrahedral manner⁷ in the crystalline 1 and 2 complexes, while 3 and 4 have a

Table 1. Cyclic voltammetric data for 2 mM copper(II)-dmp complexes in 0.1 M TBAP/absolute alcohol

Complex	Scan rate mV s ⁻¹	E_{pc1} mV	E_{pa1} mV	E_{pa2} mV	E^0 mV	ΔE_p mV	I_{pa1}/I_{pc1}
[Cu(dmp) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂ (1)	10	+620	+680		+650	60	1.0
	25	+620	+680		+650	60	0.99
	50	+610	+690		+650	80	1.0
	100	+600	+690		+640	90	0.99
	200	+590	+700		+640	110	0.98
	300	+580	+710		+645	120	1.0
[Cu(dmp) ₂ Cl]Cl.H ₂ O (3)	10	+380	+480	+610	+430	100	0.66
	25	+370	+480	+620	+425	110	0.70
	50	+360	+480	+630	+420	120	0.71
	100	+350	+490	+650	+420	140	0.72
	200	+340	+500	+670	+420	160	0.74
	300	+320	+510	+680	+415	190	0.74
[Cu(dmp) ₂ Br]Br.H ₂ O (4)	10	+590	+640		+615	50	1.0
	25	+590	+650		+620	60	1.0
	50	+590	+660		+625	70	1.0
	100	+580	+670		+625	90	1.0
	200	+570	+680		+625	110	1.0
	300	+560	+680		+620	120	1.0

$$E^0 = (E_{pc1} + E_{pa1})/2; \Delta E_p = E_{pa1} - E_{pc1}$$

Table 2. Cyclic voltammetric data for 2 mM copper(II)-dmp complexes in 0.2 M NaClO₄/50% aqueous-alcoholic medium

Complex	Scan rate mV s ⁻¹	E_{pc1} mV	E_{pa1} mV	E^0 mV	ΔE_p mV	I_{pa1}/I_{pc1}
[Cu(dmp) ₂]SO ₄ (2)	10	+460	+520	+490	60	1.0
	25	+460	+530	+495	70	1.0
	50	+460	+540	+500	80	1.0
	100	+450	+550	+500	100	1.0
	200	+440	+560	+500	120	1.0
[Cu(dmp) ₂ Br]Br.H ₂ O (4)	10	+470	+530	+500	60	0.98
	25	+470	+530	+500	60	1.0
	50	+460	+540	+500	80	1.0
	100	+450	+550	+500	100	1.0
	200	+440	+560	+500	120	0.98
	300	+430	+580	+500	150	0.98

Table 3. Cyclic voltammetric data for 2 mM [Cu(dmp)₂Cl]Cl.H₂O (3) in 0.2 M NaClO₄/50% aqueous-alcoholic medium

Scan rate mV s ⁻¹	E_{pc1} mV	E_{pc2} mV	E_{pc3} mV	E_{pc4} mV	E_{pa1} mV	E_{pa3} mV	E_{pa4} mV	E^0 mV	ΔE_p	I_{pa1}/I_{pc1}
10	+470	+240	+60	-380	+520	+270	+50	+495	60	0.75
25	+460	+225	+40	-465	+530	+280	+55	+495	70	0.80
50	+460	+210	+10	-510	+540	+280	+70	+500	80	0.83
100	+460	+190	-10	-590	+550	+290	+90	+505	90	0.80
200	+450	+160	-40	-650	+560	+290	+110	+505	110	0.80

$$\Delta E_p = E_{pa1} - E_{pc1}; I_{pc2}, I_{pc3}, I_{pa2} \text{ and } I_{pa3} \text{ are not measurable; } E^0 = (E_{pc1} + E_{pa1})/2.$$

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammogram of 2 mM [Cu(dmp)₂Cl]Cl·H₂O [A] in 0.1 M TBAP/absolute alcohol; [B] in 0.2 M NaClO₄/50% aqueous-alcoholic medium at $\nu = 50 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$.

distorted trigonal bipyramidal geometry⁷ involving 4N, Cl⁻ or Br⁻ donor atoms.

It is interesting to note that complex 3 in 0.1 M TBAP/absolute alcoholic medium shows only one reduction peak (c_1) at +360 mV vs SCE in the negative going scan while two reoxidation peaks a_1 and a_2 appear at +480 and +630 mV vs SCE ($\nu = 50 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$) in the reverse scan in the potential range from +1.0 to -0.2 V vs SCE (Table 1, Fig. 1(A)). The first anodic peak (a_1) is directly associated with the cathodic peak (c_1), while the second anodic peak (a_2) is totally irreversible. The analysis of CV data for this complex shows the following characteristics : the peak current ratio (I_{pa1}/I_{pc1}) for the Cu^{2+/+} couple is less than unity (0.66 to 0.74) and ΔE_p varies from 100 to 190 mV in the scan rate 10 to 300 mV s⁻¹ (Table 1). A plot of I_{pc1} vs $\nu^{1/2}$ gives a straight line passing through origin, indicating a diffusion-controlled single-electron transfer quasireversible electrode process. On the basis of these observations, it may therefore be concluded⁶ that the electrode process involves ECE mechanism :

An unusual and complicated electrochemical behaviour has been observed for the complex 3 in 0.2 M NaClO₄/

50% aqueous-alcoholic medium (Table 3 and Fig. 1B). The cyclic voltammogram at $\nu = 50 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$ for this complex in a negative going scan in the potential range +1.0 to -0.8 V vs SCE shows four reduction peaks c_1 , c_2 , c_3 and c_4 at +460, +210, +10 and -510 mV, respectively. The peak c_4 corresponds to reduction of Cu^I species to Cu⁰. However, two well defined anodic peaks a_1 and the characteristic stripping peak⁵, a_4 , respectively at +540 mV and +70 mV and a broad anodic hump (a_2/a_3) appear at about +230 mV (Fig. 1B). It must be noted that the potential scan of the deaerated solution of the medium only (0.2 M NaClO₄/50% aqueous-alcoholic medium also containing 2 mM dmp ligand) does not show any peak in the forward and reverse scans in the potential range +1.0 to -0.8 V vs SCE. Analysis of the CV data for the first couple (c_1/a_1) shows the following characteristic features : ΔE_p varies from 60 to 120 mV in the scan rate range 10 to 300 mV s⁻¹, I_{pa1}/I_{pc1} is ≈ 0.80 and a plot of I_{pc1} vs $\nu^{1/2}$ gives a straight line with positive intercept, indicating that the electron-transfer reaction is both preceded and followed by chemical reactions^{6,8} (CEC-mechanism). It is not possible to explain all the experimental observations at this stage. However, it is clear from CV data that solution equilibria exist and there are more than one complex species in solution⁹.

It may be noted that the reduction and oxidation peak potentials (E_{pc1}/E_{pa1}) for complexes 2, 3 and 4 in 0.2 M NaClO₄/50% aqueous-alcoholic medium are almost similar at a given scan rate (Tables 2 and 3). However, the reduction potential (E_{pc1}) in 0.1 M TBAP/absolute alcohol decreases in the order : [Cu(dmp)₂]₂(ClO₄)₂ > [Cu(dmp)₂Br]Br·H₂O > [Cu(dmp)₂Cl]Cl·H₂O.

It is interesting to note that the reduction potentials are more positive in 0.1 M TBAP/absolute alcohol as compared to that in 0.2 M NaClO₄/50% aqueous-alcoholic medium for complex 4 (Tables 1 and 2). On the other hand, reverse trend has been observed for complex 3 (Tables 1 and 3).

Polycrystalline, solution and cryogenic EPR spectral studies :

EPR spectra of powdered samples of copper(II)-dmp complexes were recorded both at room temperature (298 K) and at liquid nitrogen temperature (77 K). The EPR spectral parameters are given in Table 4. The tetrahedral complexes 1 and 2 show a single signal (Fig. 2A) which may be due to spin-spin interaction between the neighbouring paramagnetic metal ions. It is interesting to note that the g -value is greater for complex 2 than for 1 despite the fact that both these complexes have similar

Table 4. EPR spectral data for powdered samples of copper(II)-dmp complexes

Sl. no.	Complex	298 K			77 K		
		g_{\perp}	g_{\parallel}	g_{av}	g_{\perp}	g_{\parallel}	g_{av}
1.	[Cu(dmp) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	-	-	2.129	-	-	2.114
2.	[Cu(dmp) ₂]SO ₄	-	-	2.177	-	-	2.164
3.	[Cu(dmp) ₂ Cl]Cl.H ₂ O	2.184	2.003	2.124	2.194	2.003	2.130
4.	[Cu(dmp) ₂ Br]Br.H ₂ O	2.156	2.111	2.141	2.150	2.105	2.135

geometry and donor environment⁷ about the central metal ion in the solid state. It must be mentioned that EPR spectra of five coordinate complexes **3** and **4** are quite different from those of tetrahedral complexes **1** and **2**. The EPR spectra of these five coordinate trigonal bipyramidal complexes show two signals (Fig. 2B) with an intense signal (g_{\perp}) on the low field side and a less intense signal (g_{\parallel}) on the high field side, i.e. $g_{\perp} > g_{\parallel}$, analogous to those for tetragonally compressed environment with unpaired electron in d_{z^2} orbital as the ground state. It is notable that g values are greater for the chloro complex than that for the bromo analogue.

The solution and frozen solution EPR spectra of these complexes were also recorded both at RT and LNT and their EPR spectral data are collected in Table 5. A four line hyperfine isotropic EPR spectra are obtained for all these complexes in solution showing hyperfine interaction between the unpaired electron and copper nucleus ($I = 3/2$). The frozen solution spectra of all these com-

plexes, 2 mM in 0.2 M NaClO₄/50% aqueous-alcoholic medium are anisotropic axial type ($g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp}$) and $A_{\parallel} \geq 150G$ with unpaired electron in $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital as the ground state (Fig. 3A). The EPR spectrum of [Cu(dmp)₂Cl]Cl.H₂O, however, shows splitting of each of the three copper hyperfine peaks into two components in the parallel region (Fig. 3B). The splitting of the g_{\parallel} peaks may be due to presence of more than one axially or nearly axially symmetric species caused by coordinative disproportionation of [Cu(dmp)₂Cl]Cl.H₂O complex in solution. This is also well supported by our cyclic voltammetric observations (Table 3) discussed in the preceding paragraphs. The various coordination equilibria in solution are exemplified well by some complexes⁹.

Fig. 2. Polycrystalline EPR spectra of [Cu(dmp)₂](ClO₄)₂ [A], [Cu(dmp)₂Cl]Cl.H₂O [B] at LNT (77 K).

Fig. 3. Frozen solution EPR spectra of 2 mM [Cu(dmp)₂](ClO₄)₂ [A], [Cu(dmp)₂Cl]Cl.H₂O [B] in 0.2 M NaClO₄/50% aqueous-alcoholic medium at LNT (77 K).

If S represents a solvent molecule, then one or two successive solvation equilibria can exist as follows :

Table 5. Solution (0.2 M NaClO₄/50% aqueous-alcoholic) and cryogenic ESR spectral data for copper(II)-dmp complexes

Sl. no.	Complex	298 K		77 K		
		g_{iso}	$g_{ }$	g_{\perp}	g_{av}	$A_{ }^{Cu(G)}$
1.	[Cu(dmp) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	2.167	2.324	2.104	2.177	150
2.	[Cu(dmp) ₂]SO ₄	2.166	2.320	2.100	1.173	155
3.	[Cu(dmp) ₂ Cl]Cl.H ₂ O	2.191	2.311	2.094	2.166	150
4.	[Cu(dmp) ₂ Br]Br.H ₂ O	2.164	2.316	2.115	2.182	155

The tetragonally distorted octahedral nature of the solution species is, therefore, indicated by normal value of $A_{||} \geq 150G$ (Table 5).

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR or similar grade. Absolute ethyl alcohol and TBAP were supplied by Bengal Chemicals and Fluka, respectively. [Cu(dmp)₂](ClO₄)₂ (1), [Cu(dmp)₂]SO₄ (2), [Cu(dmp)₂Cl]Cl.H₂O (3) and [Cu(dmp)₂Br]Br.H₂O (4) complexes were prepared according to procedures described earlier^{7,10}. The purity of these complexes was confirmed in each case by chemical analyses. Freshly prepared solutions were used before recording the cyclic voltammograms. The working electrode was a glassy carbon electrode (GCE), platinum wire was used as an auxiliary electrode, and saturated calomel electrode (SCE) was used as a reference electrode ($E^0 = +0.242$ V vs NHE). All the experiments were performed at 25°C. Experimental details have already been described in our earlier papers^{5,8}.

A Varian E-line X-band spectrometer equipped with a dual cavity and operating in 9.152–9232 GHz range with 100 KHz modulation was used to record the EPR spectra. The g -values were calibrated with TCNE, tetracyanoethylene ($g = 2.0028$) sealed in a quartz capillary as an external standard and placed in the EPR cavity along side the sample. 2 mM solutions of each of the complex in 0.2 M NaClO₄/50% aqueous-alcoholic medium were taken for recording the EPR spectra at room temperature (298 K) and at liquid nitrogen temperature (77 K). The frozen solutions were placed in Varian liquid nitrogen Dewar flask for spectral measurements.

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References

1. K. D. Karlin, D. H. Lee and H. V. Obias, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1998, **70**, 855.
2. K. D. Karlin, S. Kaderli and A. D. Zuberbuhler, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1997, **30**, 139.
3. W. B. Tolman, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1997, **30**, 227.
4. M. A. Schwartz, J. D. Crowell and J. H. Musser, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **94**, 4363; D. Bellus, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1985, **57**, 1827.
5. B. Xie, T. Elder, L. J. Wilson and D. M. Stanbury, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1999, **38**, 12; J. Prasad, E. J. Ukpong and K. Srivastava, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2003, **80**, 751; K. Srivastava, M. Kapoor, S. Khare and J. Prasad, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **81**, 214.
6. A. J. Bard and L. R. Faulkner, "Electrochemical Methods", John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1980, pp. 229-235; R. S. Nicholson and I. Shain, *Anal. Chem.*, 1964, **36**, 706.
7. C. J. Hawkins and D. D. Perrin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 2996; J. R. Hall, N. K. Merchant and R. A. Plowman, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1963, **17**, 34; G. Davies and D. J. Loose, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, **15**, 694; J. R. Hall, N. K. Merchant and R. A. Plowman, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1962, **15**, 480.
8. K. B. Pandeya, D. Khare, J. Prasad and K. Srivastava, *Microchem. J.*, 1994, **50**, 136.
9. A. W. Addison, T. N. Rao and E. Sinn, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1984, **23**, 1957; M. F. Cabral, J. D. O. Cabral, E. Bouwman, W. L. Driessen and J. Reedijk, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1990, **167**, 205.
10. B. N. Figgis and C. M. Harries, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 855; W. Brackman and C. J. Gaasbeek, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1965, **27**, 1793; H. Elliot, B. J. Hathway and R. C. Slade, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 1443.